

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: UNITED STATES

The St. Croix Watershed Research Station

Adam Heathcote

St. Croix Watershed Research Station,
Science Museum of Minnesota
Email: aheathcote@smm.org
Twitter: @AJ_Heathcote

The St. Croix Watershed Research Station ([SCWRS](#)) is the environmental research institute of the Science Museum of Minnesota, the largest public exhibit museum in the Upper Midwest (U.S.A). Founded in 1989 as a field research station along the shoreline of the St. Croix River, it has since grown into a world class analytical laboratory and center for aquatic research. We are a small team of scientists with expertise in aquatic ecology, paleolimnology, and hydrology who work at the interface between land and water.

ering the results of that science to the public in an accessible fashion as an independent and respected scientific education institution.

In addition to the basic research produced by our scientists, our laboratories provide biological and chemical analyses for partners and collaborators around the world. The radiometric laboratory, founded by Daniel Engstrom (retired), and now overseen by Adam Heathcote, is one of the most active lake-sediment dating laboratories in the world. To date, more than 1,500 sediment cores have been dated by a combination of the radio-isotopes ^{210}Pb and ^{137}Cs spanning every continent on Earth. These dating techniques have been critical to the proliferation of paleolimnological studies that examine the impact of anthropogenic activities and contaminants to aquatic ecosystems. The microscopy laboratory, overseen by Mark Edlund, specializes in the identification and enumeration of siliceous algae (diatoms and chrysophytes) used as bioindicators in both paleo- and neo-limnological applications. Dr. Edlund and the lab are leading contributors to the Diatoms of North America taxonomic reference website (diatoms.org) and have described over sixty new diatom species based on work at SCWRS (Fig. 2).

Our scientists are currently studying some of the leading threats to aquatic ecosystems from as far away as Greenland and Mongolia to right in our backyard along the St. Croix River

Photo by Alaina Fedie

Fig. 1 SCWRS scientists sampling water quality on Lake of the Woods (Minnesota, USA) as part of a decade long collaboration between state, federal, tribal, and international agencies to determine how to best manage this ecologically and economically important water body.

As part of a non-profit museum, our research focus has evolved as we have grown and the research expertise of our staff has broadened. The mission of our museum, “Turn on the science: Inspire learning. Inform policy. Improve lives”, guides our research program and allows us to work with a diverse set of stakeholders that are concerned about the environmental condition of our aquatic resources. This includes working with state, federal, indigenous, and international agencies to provide the science needed to make the best management decisions possible (Fig. 1), and critically, deliv-

(Fig. 3). Our work is centered on doing the science most critical to protecting our lakes and streams and, importantly, as a museum we focus on how to best communicate these results in ways that are accessible to the broader public. This includes everything from interfacing with social and traditional media to helping produce exhibits on our museum floor. As a museum set in one of the most lake-rich regions of the United States, we are always looking for new ways to showcase the aquatic sciences to the public and you can follow our outreach efforts at [@sciencemuseummn](https://twitter.com/sciencemuseummn) and [@scwrs_mn](https://twitter.com/scwrs_mn) on Twitter.

Fig. 2 A living colony (left) and a single valve (right) of *Semiorbis eliasiae*, a new species of diatom recently described by SCWRS scientists and collaborators (Edlund et al. 2021) and found in a long-shore embayment of Lake Superior's Apostle Islands National Park (Outer Island, Wisconsin, USA).

Photo by N. John Anderson

Some Recent Publications

Edlund MB, Burge DRL, Andresen NA, Vandermeulen DD, Stone JR, Van de Vijver B. 2021. The genus *Semiorbis* (Eunatiaceae, Bacillariophyta) in North America. *Diatom Research* 36: 39-50.

Edlund MB, Jude DJ, Nalepa TF. 2021. Diets of the benthic amphipod *Diporeia* in southern Lake Michigan before and after the dreissenid invasion. *Journal of Great Lakes Research* 47: 447-462.

Justus, BG, Driver L, Burge DRL. 2021. Seasonal periphyton response to low-level nutrient exposure in a least disturbed mountain stream, the Buffalo River, Arkansas. *Ecological Indicators* 121: p107150.

Anderson NJ, Engstrom DR, Leavitt PR, Flood S, Heathcote AJ. 2020. Changes in coupled carbon-nitrogen dynamics in a tundra ecosystem predate recent regional warming. *Nature Communications Earth & Environment* 1: 38.

Wang M, Bao K, Heathcote AJ, Zhu Q, Cheng G, Li S, Zhang C. 2020. Spatio-temporal pattern of metal contamination in Chinese lakes since 1850. *Catena* 196: 104918.

Anderson NJ, Heathcote AJ, Engstrom DR, GLOBOCARB Data Contributors. 2020. Anthropogenic alteration of nutrient supply increases the global freshwater carbon sink. *Science Advances* 6: eaaw2145.

Stone, JR, Edlund, MB and Alverson, AJ. 2020. *Fascinorbis* gen. nov., a new genus of Stephanodiscaceae (Bacillariophyta) from a Late Miocene lacustrine diatomite. *Diatom Research* 35: 127-139.

Lapierre J, Heathcote AJ, Maisonneuve P, Filstrup CT. 2019. Is limnology becoming increasingly abiotic, riverine, and global? *Limnology and Oceanography Letters* 5: 204-211.

Saros JE, Anderson NJ, Juggins S, McGowan S, Yde JC, Telling J, Bullard JE, Yallop ML, Heathcote AJ, Burpee BT, Fowler RA, Barry CD, Northington RM, Osburn CL, Pla-Rabes S, Mernild SH, Whiteford EJ, Andrews MG, Kerby JT, Post E. 2019. Arctic climate shifts drive rapid ecosystem responses across the West Greenland landscape. *Environmental Research Letters* 14: 074027

Strock, KE, Saros, JE, McGowan, S, Edlund, MB, Engstrom DR. 2019. Response of boreal lakes to changing wind strength: Coherent physical changes across two large lakes but varying effects on primary producers over the 20th century. *Limnology and Oceanography* 64: 2237-2251.

Siver PA, Wolfe AP, Edlund MB, Sibley J, Hausman J, Torres P, Lott AM. 2019. *Aulacoseria giraffensis* sp. nov., a new diatom species forming massive populations in a middle Eocene lake. *Plant Ecology and Evolution* 152: 358-367.

Alexson EA, Reavie ED, Axler RP, Yements SY, Krasutsky PA, Edlund MB, Pillsbury RW and Desotelle D. 2018. Paleolimnology of a freshwater estuary to inform Area of Concern nutrient delisting efforts. *Journal of Paleolimnology* 59(3): 373-395.

Photo by Alaina Fedie

Fig. 3 (Top) SCWRS scientist Adam Heathcote and students from Newcastle University (UK) mapping a remote lake in Southwest Greenland as part of an international expedition measuring the effects of climate change on lakes. (Bottom) SCWRS scientists collecting a piston core from Bad Medicine Lake (Minnesota, USA) as part of a paleolimnological study to look at the effect of introduced fish species on lower trophic levels.

Edlund MB, Burge DRL. 2019. Polymorphism in *Mastogloia* (Bacillariophyceae) revisited. *Plant Ecology and Evolution* 152: 351-357.

Edlund MB, Schottler SP, Reavie ED, Engstrom DR, Baratono NG, Leavitt PR, Heathcote AJ, Wilson B, Paterson AM. 2017. Historical phosphorus dynamics in Lake of the Woods (USA-Canada) – does legacy phosphorus still affect the southern basin? *Lake and Reservoir Management* 33: 386-402.

Burge, DRL, Edlund MB, Frisch D. 2017. Paleolimnology and resurrection ecology: The future of reconstructing the past. *Evolutionary Applications* 11: 42-59.

<https://www.smm.org/scwrs>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889852>